

A method for transforming rice stinkbug counts in rice

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Most statistical procedures presuppose a normal distribution, with variance independent of mean insect population. However, in field counts of a majority of insect species, variance varies as a power function of the population (Taylor 1961). Such data have to be transformed before analysis to eliminate the dependence of the variance on the mean population.

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of aggregation parameter b -based transformation in breaking the dependence of population variance on the mean density of rice stinkbug *Leptocorisa varicornis* F. and to compare its performance with routinely used logarithmic transformations. The present investigation was carried out using rice variety Pusa-834 during the rainy seasons of 2001 and 2002 at IARI. The experiment involved two sets (Set 1 and Set 2) in the first year and one set (Set 3) in the second year, each set containing 40 $2 \text{ m} \times 1.5\text{-m}$ quadrats. One-month-old seedlings were transplanted in well-puddled fields on 18 Jul 2001 and 20 Jul 2002 at $15 \times 20\text{-cm}$ spacing. NPK was applied at $120\text{-}60\text{-}40 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ and the crop was irrigated as required. No pesticide was applied.

The populations of nymphs and adults of *L. varicornis* were recorded on

10 randomly selected hills in every quadrat at 5-d intervals after flowering until the pests disappeared. The population counts so obtained were multiplied by 3 to derive a population estimate for a $1 \text{ m} \times 1\text{-m}$ area as each quadrat contained about 30 hills (Ruesink and Kogan 1982).

The mean population (M) and variance (S^2) were determined for combined nymphal and adult populations observed at each observation. Taylor's power law (Taylor 1961) was fitted to mean population and variance data of Set 1 and sampling parameter a and aggregation parameter b were determined. The original pest counts (X) of each of the 40 quadrats for every observation were transformed by $\log(X + 1)$ and

$\chi^{1-b/2}$ transformations. The value of b obtained from the data of Set 1 was used for transforming the original pest counts of sets 2 and 3. The mean and variance were worked out for transformed counts with each method of transformation. The appropriateness of these transformations was examined by computing simple correlation coefficient r between the variance and mean of original counts as well as transformed counts. The chi-square test (Barlett's test) for testing the homogeneity of sampling variances in each set was also carried out (Gomez and Gomez 1984).

The values of a and b were found to be 1.1429 ($\log a = 0.058$) and 1.5048, respectively, in Set 1 (see figure). A

Fig. 1. Determination of Taylor's power law parameters for rice stinkbug *Leptocorisa varicornis*.

Table 1. Population mean and variance of original and transformed counts of *Leptocorisca varicornis* infesting Pusa 834, 2001 rainy season.^a

Sample	Set 1						Set 2					
	Original count (X)		Log (X + 1)-transformed count		$X^{1-b/2}$ -transformed count (b = 1.5048)		Original count (X)		Log (X + 1)-transformed count		$X^{1-b/2}$ -transformed count (b = 1.5048)	
	M	S ²	M	S ²	M	S ²	M	S ²	M	S ²	M	S ²
1	0.9	1.015	0.218	0.054	0.572	0.341	0.97	1.056	0.236	0.053	0.626	0.326
2	1.4	1.579	0.316	0.061	0.593	0.608	1.5	1.538	0.341	0.054	0.872	0.276
3	2.0	2.692	0.411	0.068	0.977	0.270	1.95	2.726	0.393	0.074	0.926	0.316
4	3.0	9.974	0.484	0.103	1.070	0.305	2.77	7.513	0.470	0.098	1.041	0.324
5	1.2	1.533	0.271	0.059	0.843	0.294	1.55	1.741	0.335	0.070	0.798	0.360
6	1.8	1.856	0.379	0.071	0.875	0.345	1.05	1.279	0.248	0.056	0.655	0.336
7	0.45	0.408	0.126	0.029	0.389	0.261	0.32	0.277	0.095	0.022	0.257	0.239
Chi-square	$\chi^2 = 119.8$ ($P < 0.01$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 15.13$ ($P < 0.05$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 7.21$ ($P > 0.05$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 109.2$ ($P < 0.01$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 81.7$ ($P < 0.01$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 2.18$ ($P > 0.05$, 6 df)	
Correlation	$r = 0.883$ ($P < 0.01$, 5 df)		$r = 0.941$ ($P < 0.01$, 5 df)		$r = -0.254$ ($P > 0.05$, 5 df)		$r = 0.911$ ($P < 0.01$, 5 df)		$r = 0.954$ ($P < 0.01$, 5 df)		$r = 0.455$ ($P > 0.05$, 5 df)	

^aM = mean population, S² = variance, df = degrees of freedom.

Table 2. Population mean and variance of original and transformed counts of *Leptocorisca varicornis* infesting Pusa 834, 2002 rainy season.^a

Sample	Set 3					
	Original count (X)		Log (X + 1)-transformed count		$X^{1-b/2}$ -transformed count b = 1.5048	
	M	S ²	M	S ²	M	S ²
1	1.07	1.097	0.261	0.051	0.703	0.314
2	1.55	1.843	0.345	0.057	0.876	0.281
3	2.02	3.256	0.399	0.079	0.931	0.323
4	2.97	9.563	0.482	0.104	1.054	0.337
5	1.22	2.692	0.261	0.069	0.668	0.358
6	1.75	3.167	0.350	0.083	0.813	0.381
7	0.52	1.589	0.108	0.049	0.267	0.261
Chi-square	$\chi^2 = 68.98$ ($P < 0.01$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 13.14$ ($P < 0.05$, 6 df)		$\chi^2 = 2.002$ ($P > 0.05$, 6 df)	
Correlation	$r = 0.881$ ($P < 0.01$, 5 df)		$r = 0.834$ ($P < 0.05$, 5 df)		$r = 0.478$ ($P > 0.05$, 5 df)	

^aM = mean population, S² = variance, df = degrees of freedom.

value of b greater than 1.0 revealed an aggregated pest distribution on the crop. The mean and variance of original bug counts as well as log (X + 1)-transformed counts in the three sets were highly correlated (Tables 1 and 2). The

logarithmic transformation thus proved ineffective in reducing the dependence of variance on stinkbug mean population. However, the aggregation parameter b -based transformation eliminated the dependence of variance on

mean population as correlation coefficient values between the mean and variance of b -transformed counts in three sets were nonsignificant ($r = -0.253, 0.455, \text{ and } 0.478$, respectively). The chi-square values for the homogeneity test of sample variances of original counts in three sets (119.8, 109.2, and 67.9, respectively) were significant, thus indicating that sample variances were not homogeneous (Tables 1 and 2). Likewise, chi-square values for the homogeneity test of sample variances of log (X + 1)-transformed counts in three sets (15.13, 81.75, and 13.14, respectively) were also significant, reflecting nonhomogeneity of the variances. However, chi-square values for homogeneity of sample variances of $X^{1-b/2}$ -transformed counts in three sets (7.21, 2.18, and 2.0, respectively) were nonsignificant,

showing homogeneity of the sample variances. The aggregation parameter-based transformation of the rice bug field counts thus proved effective in normalizing the sample variances. Often, logarithmic transformation is used for normalizing population variance without caring for its validity, which may produce spurious results. However,

the use of aggregation parameters for the transformation of insect counts will be useful in overcoming this lacuna.

References

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Weed control in direct, dry-seeded rice in India: comparison of seedbed preparation and use of pendimethalin

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Under direct seeding in dry-bed conditions, weeds are a major constraint to rice productivity because rice and weeds germinate almost simultaneously. Grassy weeds are also more difficult to remove by hand because their morphology is similar to that of rice. Weeds have reportedly reduced yield of dry-seeded rice by 15–60% (Moody 1982). Direct-seeded rice covers 26% and 28% of the total rice area in South Asia and India, respectively (Pandey and Velasco 1999). Thus, appropriate weed control measures will be of immense importance to the farming community. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of weed management practices on the productivity and profitability of aerobic rice, particularly in places where labor is scanty and costly.

A field experiment was conducted during the 2001-02 kharif at the project site in Uttar Pradesh on sandy loam soil (Typic Ustochrept). Treatments were laid out in a split-plot design replicated thrice. Variety Pant Dhan 12 was sown at 60 kg seed ha⁻¹ under aerobic conditions. Two seedbed practices (stale seedbed and traditional seedbed) were used as the main plot. To prepare the stale seedbed after the rabi crop harvest in April, the field was irrigated once. Two cross harrowings + one cultivator + one planking were then performed. The field was left for germination of weed seeds for about 15 d, after which the field was finally prepared by one shallow plowing with the cultivator, followed by planking. In the traditional method, at sowing time, two harrowings

+ two cultivator + one planking were done to prepare a well-pulverized seedbed. Five weed control methods (hand weeding twice, herbicide + one hand weeding, criss-cross seeding + one hand weeding, criss-cross seeding + one hand weeding + herbicide, and unweeded check) were assigned to subplots. A uniform dose of fertilizer was applied basally—37 kg N, 26.4 kg P, 49.8 kg K, and 4.6 kg Zn ha⁻¹. Nitrogen was applied in two 53-kg doses at 25 d after sowing (DAS) and at 55–60 DAS. The herbicide (pendimethalin 35% EC at 4 L ha⁻¹) was sprayed 1–2 d after seeding. Hand weeding was done at 25 DAS and at 50–55 DAS. Weed samples were collected from two places at random in a 1-m² area and weed dry weight (oven-dry basis) was assessed.